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ORAL PRESENTATIONS

STATIC AND DYNAMIC BALANCE ASSESSMENT WITH AND WITHOUT BRACE IN A GIRL WITH IDIOPATHIC SCOLIOSIS- CASE REPORT

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Introduction: Proper posture enables adequate balance and body stability with minimal muscle effort. As scoliosis is a three-dimensional spinal deformity that affects posture, the aim of this study was to analyze balance performance in a girl with idiopathic scoliosis (IS) in conditions with and without a brace. Due to subjective issues during testing in clinical settings, we utilized a motion analysis system in the laboratory.

Materials and methods: A 12-year-old girl with right thoracic IS (Cobb's angle 35,1°) who is treated with Rigo-Cheneau brace was assessed. Static and dynamic balance assessments were performed using the Single Leg Stance (SLS), Four Square Step Test (FSST) and Y Balance Test (YBT). The testing took place in the laboratory at the Faculty of Technical Sciences, Novi Sad using the Vicon motion capture system (©Vicon Motion Systems Ltd., UK).

Results: There was no difference in SLS with eyes open (60 sec achieved with and without brace on both legs), while SLS with eyes closed on the right leg was better with brace (9 sec vs 4 sec). On the FSST the girl performed faster without a brace (8 sec vs 10 sec). On the YBT, greater reach in the anterior direction was achieved on the right leg with brace (71.25 cm vs 62.13 cm), as well as on the left leg in the postero-medial direction with brace (77.61cm vs 61.15cm). In other directions, greater reach was achieved without brace on both legs.

Conclusion: The assessment of static and dynamic balance using the Vicon system provides measurement precision. Our research showed that balance was better in some aspects with the brace, but it restricted trunk movements and consequently had a negative impact on balance in other aspects. Further research is needed to draw conclusions about balance in IS and the impact of bracing on balance.

Keywords: balance, balance tests, Vicon, scoliosis, brace